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*Identification and Model Construction of the Drivers of Sustainable Development of
Library in Maker Space —Empirical Analysis Based on The Grounded Theory*

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ABSTRACT

The article uses the grounded theory and method to refine the category of the driver factors of the sustainable development of the library's maker space as the main line, and takes the Nvivo three-level node coding as the traction, focusing on the construction of the model of sustainable development. To conduct field research on the maker space of public libraries, university libraries and social institutions in China, select 102 experienced librarians/ makers with excellent work performance to obtain interview data, using open coding, spindle coding and selective coding to extract concepts and categories; According to the standard flow code analysis, identify the sustainable development of library space drivers. On the basis of this, we construct the driver model (CACS) for the sustainable development of library's maker space, and explain the model. Then, SPSS24 .0 was used for correlation analysis to verify the identification results of the grounded theory. Which provided reference for library to explore driving factors, reducing development resistance, and improve service efficiency.

INTRODUCTION

"Sustainable development" means that the development of human society should realize the coordination and adaptation of information, education, ecology, resources, social economy and population. The theory of sustainable development is a new idea, theory and concept for human to explore permanent development. It also has great influence on human's world outlook, development outlook and values [1]. The main functions of library's creative space are knowledge innovation, technological innovation, knowledge dissemination and knowledge application, which match the core ideas and functions of sustainable development, and the creative space has high-quality elements of sustainable development, such as the support and guarantee of national policies, rich information resources, high-quality information talents, innovative services and innovative capabilities, superior innovative environment and influence, etc. These elements and resources exist more or less in different types of library's creative space. As long as space managers follow the trend and give full play to their advantages, these elements will become the driving force for the sustainable development of space, so that the creative space will develop in an orderly and long-term manner in China. It can be predicted that in the future, the idea and theory of sustainable development will become the core idea to promote the development and growth of library visitor space.

Put forward research questions

Shanghai Library Creation New Space is the first creative space in China, born in May 2013, since then, the academic field of libraries has set off a huge upsurge of research, greatly enriching the theoretical

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research and practical activities of creative space.

Compared with the developed capitalist our country is still in the exploration stage because of the restriction of many factors, and because of lacking rich practical experience and theoretical guidance, various problems will inevitably be exposed in the development process, such as the asymmetry of service demand and supply, the lack of professional ability of librarians, the low quality and level of service, the imperfect mechanism of fund guarantee, the insufficient training atmosphere and the unclear function orientation[2]. Jiang Yiyi[3]pointed out that the short board of the construction of creating guest space in domestic university library is: The service content is rich but lacks the depth, each project is not deep enough, the basic reason that causes this phenomenon is: lacks the powerful guidance of the professional theory, the talent selection system is imperfect, the support strength which the country and the government give is small and so on. Kou Yin et al[4]Through the investigation of the operation of the creative space of public and university libraries in our country, the following conclusions are drawn: The construction and development of the creative space of libraries in our country is very difficult, we can draw lessons from the successful experience of other developed countries, introduce scientific theoretical guidance system, pay more attention to the interpretation of cases, mechanism guarantee, function utilization and planning design, and fundamentally improve the service quality and level of the creative space. As of October 12, 2019, the author found that in the past three years, 380 academic papers have been published on the Internet with the theme of "Library Creator Space Development", and only 35 papers with the title of "Library Creator Space Development", accounting for only 0. The result of literature retrieval with the title of "Sustainable Development of Library Creator Space" is 1, entitled "Research on the Construction and Sustainable Development of Library Creator Space in Small and Medium-sized Libraries", which studies the sustainable development of library Creator Space from the perspective of "driving factors", At present, the search result of literature on cnki is 0. It can be seen that, first, the current research results focus on the research service model more, research service effect less; second, the theoretical basis for the theme of research less, the lack of accurate theoretical system structure and guidance; third, the lack of qualitative and quantitative combination of research, research methods to qualitative; in short, the lack of relevant theoretical support and guidance is part of our library visitor space development lag or slow.

Based on this, this paper introduces the idea and theory of sustainable development, and uses scientific theory to arm and guide the practice of library visitor space, emphasizes the development trend of diversification and refinement in the research content, identifies the development motive force of library visitor space from the perspective of driving factors, which is the source of service effect, and launches multi-level research on development driving factors, so as to provide more valuable reference materials for improving the service effect of space; Qualitative and quantitative empirical methods are used to identify the driving factors of spatial sustainable development, and then quantitative methods are used to verify the reliability and validity of the research results. The whole research idea is: firstly, using grounded theory and method, abstracting the category of spatial sustainable development driving factors as the main line, using Nvivo12 three-level node coding as the traction, carrying on coding analysis to interview data, identifying the driving factors of spatial sustainable development; then on the basis of pre-coding, constructing spatial sustainable development driving factors model (CACS) and explaining; finally using SPSS24.0 to carry out correlation analysis, verify the identification results of grounded theory, facilitate space managers to tap driving factors, reduce development resistance, innovate service system and mechanism, and improve the service efficiency of library customer space from the root.

Research methods and data collection

Research methods

Grounded theory is put forward by the well-known foreign scholar Glass, that is, based on previous research data, actively explore the core concepts that can fully reflect social phenomena, and on this basis, construct the relevant social theory [5]. Grounded method emphasizes that the theory comes from data, Glaser, a well-known foreign scholar, believes that memos, questionnaires, observations, literature, reflection and interviews are original data, through classification, induction and analysis of

original data, layer by layer to sum up the theory.

The biggest difference with other theories is that grounded theory collects data, analyses data and produces theories at the same time, in short, after each data is obtained, researchers analyze it within a set time, compare it with existing categories and concepts, and use it as the basis for collecting data and selecting samples. The whole process of data analysis, commonly known as coding, is a series of dynamic process of data decomposition, conceptualization and recombination, which is helpful to the subsequent theoretical analysis and verification. It emphasizes the triple coding technology for theoretical construction, coding is divided into three stages: open coding, spindle coding, selective coding. In Nvivo12 corresponding to the primary coding (first level coding), two level coding, three level coding three stages, has formed a free node (child node). Deep interview is an efficient method of data collection, which can get close contact with the subjects and fully understand their work experience, life experience and so on, so as to collect the original data and provide sufficient theoretical basis for the follow-up study[6].

Interviews

This study selects the interviewees according to the theoretical sampling method, that is, according to the analytical framework of grounded theory and the specific requirements of concept induction to determine the interviewees[7]. Members of the research group conducted field research on the creation and operation of 12 public libraries, 16 university libraries, 1 professional library and 7 social institutions in China, all of which have been constructed and operated for about two years or more, some of which have been longer, such as the creation and new space of Shanghai Library, which was constructed in May 2013 and has been seven years so far. The members of the research group selected some excellent librarians and creators as the interview objects to conduct in-depth interviews, including 5 from Chengdu Library Reading Creation Space, 1 from Changsha Library New Triangle Creation Space, 5 from Guangzhou Library Creation Space, 4 from Shenzhen Library Creation Space, 6 from Hangzhou Library Creation Space, 6 from Jiaying Library Digital Public Creation Space and 9 from Shenyang Normal University. Seven people come from Jingdong Creator Space of Shanghai Jiaotong University Library, six from Shanghai Maritime University Library Creator Space, seven from Three Gorges University Library Creator Space, six from Southwest Jiaotong University Engineering Training Center Creator Space, five from National Defense University Library Creator Space, eight from Nanjing University of Technology Creator Space, four from Tsinghua University School of Economics and Management Accelerator, and six from Tianjin University. Six people came from the entrepreneurship base of Guangzhou University of Technology, five from the creative space of Anhui University Library, and six from the cultural creation space of Tongling Library, totaling 102 people.

Reserch steps

This paper uses in-depth interviews to collect literature to provide a sufficient theoretical basis for the later study; on this basis, the use of grounded theory coding, induction category. The concrete operation steps are as follows: first, sort out and analyze the relevant literature about sustainable development in domestic and foreign library visitor space, form the outline of semi-structured interview; select the interview object according to the principle of grounded sampling survey, and form the complete interview data by recording or recording; then code the interview data according to the relevant requirements, establish the core category, and explore the relationship between different categories from many different angles. Identify and summarize the driving factors of sustainable development of library visitor space; Finally, construct the "consciousness-atmosphere-cost-field" driving factor model of sustainable development of space, and the driving factor model (CACS). Explain.

Data collection

The data analysis and processing of this paper is divided into two stages: the first stage is from October 2017 to August 2018, and the second stage is from September 2018 to July 2019. In the first stage, the members of the research group selected 102 experienced and outstanding librarians and creators from various regions of China in batches to conduct in-depth interviews. After the interview, the interview records were sorted out, qualitatively analyzed according to the criteria of grounded theory, and three-level coding and category refinement were carried out. In-depth interviews took the form of group interviews and one-to-one interviews, with an average interview time of 60 minutes for each team and 40 minutes for one-to-one interviews.

Semi-structured interview is a kind of informal interview with the characteristics of flexibility, flexibility and openness. Generally speaking, the interviewees are not restricted by the questions in the interview outline[8]. It is easier to draw in the distance from the interviewees, grasp the facts and lay a foundation for the abstract treatment of the follow-up categories and concepts. On the basis of previous literature analysis, a preliminary draft of semi-structured interview outline was formed, and then 12 librarians and creators of the Creative Space of Wuhan University Library and the Creative Space of Shanghai Library were investigated in advance to understand his (her) different experiences and gains in space construction and development, and the semi-structured interview outline was revised, and finally a final draft was formed, and 102 librarians and creators were formally interviewed in depth to understand him (her). During the whole interview process, the members of the research group focus on the outline of the interview and communicate with the interviewees

in depth, mainly focusing on the driving factors of the sustainable development of library visitor space, and the interviewees (librarians/visitors) This paper introduces their cognition and feelings about the driving factors of space sustainable development through narrative[9]. The interview questions mainly involve: the perception of the function orientation, leadership attention, responsibility identification and individual cognition of space sustainable development, the knowledge and experience of the infrastructure, source of funds, economic cost, economic benefit and convenience of space sustainable development, etc; The management system, operation mechanism, service items, personnel allocation and resource allocation of space sustainable development are described, and the driving atmosphere of space sustainable development, such as government support, security policies, public opinion propaganda and implementation intensity, is evaluated. After the interview, the members of the research group converted the interview recordings into text information in time, and obtained a total of 190000 words of interview records through collation, according to these interview records, taking into account the distribution of various regions in China (eastern, western, central, southern and northern), randomly selected interview records, coded and analyzed them professionally according to the rules formulated in advance, and another 6 interview records were used to test the saturation of the theory. Interviews and coding are carried out alternately, that is, coding is carried out immediately after each librarian's interview is completed, and the coding process is carried out by repeatedly reading and comparing the interview text and coding data until the theory is saturated, that is, no new concepts and relations appear, then the coding is stopped.

Identification of the driving factors of sustainable development of library's creative space

To ensure the standardization, systematization and standardization of the data analysis process, the research team introduced NVivo12 software into the coding process.

Reference Points, Coverage and Pearson Correlation Coefficients of Node Codes

This paper uses Nvivo12 software, through the first node coding (selective coding), the second node coding (principal axis coding), the third node coding (open coding) three stages, obtained four first node, six second node, three nodes 27. The frequency of each node, coverage and Pearson correlation coefficient, see table 1、 Figure 1 for details. Among them, Pearson correlation coefficient usually refers to the correlation relationship between nodes, generally, 0.5 to 0.8 belong to strong correlation, 0.8-1.0 is extremely strong correlation. Through the observation of table 5, we can find that Pearson coefficients are between 0-0.99, it is not difficult to see that these elements nodes show strong correlation relationship. In the distribution map of node coding hierarchy of spatial sustainable development drivers, the proportion size and structure distribution of each coding reference point are shown in detail, and the important comparison and influential relationship of each coding reference point (node) in spatial sustainable development are clear and clear at a glance. Among them, the management system, operation mechanism, service items, personnel allocation, resource allocation and platform function in the field drive have higher values of coding reference point, coverage rate and Pearson correlation coefficient, especially in the distribution map of coding level, accounting for about 65%, which shows that in the process of spatial sustainable development, these factors have the strongest driving influence and should be paid attention and guided.

Table 1 Reference Points, Coverage and Pearson Correlation Coefficients for Nodal Coding

Primary Node Code (Selective coding)	Secondary Node Code (Spindle Code)	Three-level Node Code (Open Encoding)	Encoding Reference Points	Coverage (%)	Pearson coefficient correlation
Consciousness Factor	Driving Consciousness	Leaders attach importance to	281	17.87	0.997887
		Function Orientation	451	25.67	0.998218
		Individual Cognition	204	23.92	0.992688
		Responsibility Identification	423	24.8	0.998038
		Effectiveness Perception	357	22.41	0.978526
Cost Factor	Driving Cost	Infrastructure	235	19.98	0.993626
		Source of funds	180	21.35	0.990827
		Economic Cost	121	16.52	0.983824
		Economic Benefit	52	16.48	0.976774
		Associated Risk	19	23.14	0.971412
		Convenience	351	21.63	0.997486
Atmosphere Factor	Driving Atmosphere	Government Support	118	17.86	0.987195
		Safeguard Policy	122	15.18	0.989289
		Public Opinion Propaganda	281	20.69	0.996278
		Service Effect	381	22.96	0.998245
		Enforcement Strength	349	21.96	0.973753
		Group Constraint	132	71.34	0.975716
Field Field Factor	Driving Field	Management System	428	25.27	0.999026
		Operating Mechanism	419	23.43	0.999026
		Service Items	556	27.59	0.998746
		Resource Allocation	524	26.37	0.997141
		Staffing	316	22.29	0.997167
		Platform Function	1154	24.36	0.997854

Note: The second level node code reference points is the sum of its own code reference points and the subordinate third level node code reference points.

Figure 1 Distribution of node coding hierarchy of spatial sustainability drivers

Theoretical Saturation Test

After four months, the members of the research group completed the interview and coding of the 96th librarian/creator, carried out continuous analysis, revision or supplement of the existing theoretical assumptions, and found that no new concepts and relationships appeared. In order to enhance the accuracy, representativeness and practicality of

the study, the author randomly sampled the work logs, observation notes and interview records of six librarians, and tested their saturation by professional means. The test results showed that no new relationships, concepts and constituent elements appeared again, thus judging that the theory formed by the coding process had reached saturation.

Model Construction and Explanation of the Driving Factors of Sustainable Development of Library Creator Space

Model Construction

In this paper, we use the method of reading relevant literature and interview survey, collate and analyze the data obtained from the research questions, establish a perfect context structure with the steps of selective coding, spindle coding and open coding, explore the relationship between concepts, sub-categories and main categories from multiple perspectives and levels, and finally form four selective coding, and based on the story line. This paper constructs a "consciousness-atmosphere-cost-field" driving factor model for the sustainable development of library visitor space, as shown in Figure 2, which is called CACS (Consciousness-Atmosphere- Cost-System). Through the study, we can see that the field factor, atmosphere factor, cost factor and consciousness factor are the key factors affecting the long-term development of Creator Space, and the corresponding categories of these four factors are field-driven, atmosphere-driven, cost-driven and consciousness-driven. Among them, consciousness drive includes five driving factors of function orientation, leadership attention, individual cognition, responsibility identity and effectiveness perception; cost drive includes six driving factors of infrastructure, source of funds, economic cost, economic benefit, convenience and related risks; atmosphere drive includes six driving factors of government support, guarantee policy, service effect, public opinion propaganda, execution intensity and group restraint. Field drive includes management system, operation mechanism, service items, personnel allocation, resource allocation and platform function.

Figure 2 The driving factor model of "consciousness-atmosphere-cost-field" for sustainable development of library creative space

Model interpretation

The basic function relation contained in the model is that consciousness factor, cost factor, atmosphere factor and field driving factor have significant influence on the sustainable development of library visitor space, and the four driving forces formed by these four factors are consciousness driving, cost driving, atmosphere driving and field driving, which are the driving sources of space sustainable development, among which consciousness driving is external power, field driving is internal power and cost driving is internal binding force. Atmosphere drive is the external binding force. These are the

driving forces of library creating space, which determine and affect the speed and direction of sustainable development of space, in which the field drive is the core driving force of sustainable development of space, and plays a leading role in sustainable development of space, which can be verified and explained by SPSS in the later period.

Model validation of drivers

Issuance and recovery of questionnaires

According to the model of driving factors of sustainable development constructed by grounded research, the members of the research group compiled a questionnaire of "driving factors of sustainable development of library visitor space", which consists of three parts: introduction, personal basic information and variable measurement. The variables are measured according to Likert's five-level scale, that is, "very satisfactory, relatively satisfactory, general, not very satisfactory, very unsatisfactory", corresponding to "1, 2, 3, 4, 5" to assign scores, and the selection design of relevant variables measurement indicators is shown in Table 2.

From October 2017 to July 2019, online questionnaires and field research activities were carried out in universities, public and professional libraries in China, and 720 questionnaires were recovered, of which 346 were librarians and 374 were creators; invalid questionnaires were eliminated: 4 were librarians and 3 were creators, 713 were valid questionnaires, of which 342 were librarians and 371 were creators; the effective recovery rate was 99%.0 Complete the empirical analysis.

Table 2 Design and Description of Measurement Indexes for Driver Variables

Factor	Variables	Measurement option definition
Consciousness Drive	Leaders attach importance to	Importance and support of leaders at all levels for sustainable space development
	Function Orientation	Building and developing space with the concept of openness, sharing, cooperation and innovation
	Individual Cognition	The Interest and Enthusiasm of Librarians/Creators in the Sustainable Development of Space
	Responsibility Identification	Librarian/Creator's sense of responsibility to participate in the sustainable development of space
	Effectiveness Perception	Perceptions of Librarians/Creators on the effectiveness or impact of sustainable spatial development
Cost-drive	Infrastructure	Configuration of relevant equipment, tools and materials necessary for sustainable development of space
	Source of funds	Various sources of funds (state, government, school, industry, enterprise, etc.)
	Economic Cost	Construction and development of customer space needs to pay a certain cost of capital.
	Economic Benefit	Value-added benefits after the use of funds (economic benefits and influence of creative products or works, etc.)
	Convenience	Is the location, layout and design of space convenient and conducive to the sustainable development of space?
	Associated Risk	Sustainable space development entails some investment risks or losses, such as intellectual property rights and security risks.
Atmosphere drive	Government Support	The government's attention and support to the sustainable development of space
	Safeguard Policy	The degree of policy guarantee for the sustainable development of space
	Public Opinion Propaganda	Space plays a role of publicity and promotion, and raises attention.
	Service Effect	Librarians' quality and ability improvement, social benefits and social influence, etc.
	Enforcement Strength	Implementation of planning, objectives and systems for sustainable space development
	Group Constraint	The Leading and Demonstrative Role of Other Public and University Libraries in Creating Customer Space
Field-drive	Management System	Management system for sustainable space development (the role of the current management system in promoting space development)
	Operating Mechanism	The operation of assessment, evaluation, feedback and performance management mechanism of spatial sustainable development
	Service Items	Planning and Implementation of Service Items and Service Channels for Sustainable Development of Space

Staffing	Allocation of full-time/part-time librarians for sustainable development of space (whether to set up full-time Creator Librarians)
Resource Allocation	Configuration of hardware and software resources for sustainable development of space (such as open large space, group seminar room and individual research room)
Platform Function	Hardware and Software Facilities and System Stability of Sustainable Development Service Platform

SPSS Empirical Analysis

Reliability and validity analysis

Reliability is an index reflecting the consistency and stability of the data. The reliability criterion is Cronbach's Alpha coefficient ≥ 0.7 , which indicates that the data has good stability and consistency. The validity of KMO, Bartlett's test and the most generous difference method are selected to analyze the questionnaire. If KMO value ≥ 0.7 , the structure validity of the test content is good. The reliability and validity were analyzed and the results were as shown in Table 3: the overall value was 0.979, and the α value of each module was above 0.7, which indicated that the data had high credibility; the Bartlett spherical test was significant when the significance was about 1%, and the KMO values of each module and the overall were all above 0.7, which indicated that the structure of each module was good.

Table 3 Test results of reliability effect

Variables	Number of items	Cronbach's α	Global Cronbach's α	KMO value	Global KMO value	Sig.
Consciousness Drive	5	0.927	0.979	0.902	0.973	0.000
Cost-driven	6	0.939		0.902		0.000
Atmosphere driven	6	0.940		0.922		0.000
Field-driven	6	0.937		0.928		0.000

Descriptive statistics

In this study, the average score and standard deviation of 23 variables of library sustainable development driving factors were calculated, and the calculated results were arranged according to the average value gradually increasing from left to right. See Table 4 for details. According to the above scoring principle, the lower the average score, the stronger the driving effect of this indicator on sustainable development, and the smaller the standard deviation, the closer the recognition of this driving effect by most librarians and creators.

Table 4 Drivers mean, standard deviation statistics (N = 713)

Variables	Mean	Standard	Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation
Platform	1.74	0.844	Safeguard Policy	1.90	0.905
Management	1.74	0.789	Enforcement Strength	1.93	0.803
Operating	1.82	0.905	Source of funds	1.93	0.864
Service Items	1.83	0.813	Service Effect	1.93	0.929
Staffing	1.83	0.813	Public Opinion	1.95	1.013
Resource	1.86	0.820	Economic Cost	1.96	0.888
Leaders attach	1.86	0.829	Infrastructure	1.96	0.921
Function	1.87	0.807	Economic Benefit	1.97	0.865
Individual	1.87	0.811	Convenience	1.98	0.949
Responsibility	1.87	0.832	Group Constraint	2.06	0.984
Effectiveness	1.88	0.876	Associated Risk	2.07	0.977
Government	1.90	0.881			

Table 4 shows that among the 23 indicators, only the group constraint and related risks are between "relatively satisfactory" and "average"; the other indicators are between "very satisfactory" and "relatively satisfactory", and tend to be "relatively satisfactory".

Correlation analysis

With the above 23 indicators as independent variables, driving factors as dependent variables, in SPSS24.0, each independent variable and driving factors were analyzed, Pearson coefficient and bilateral significance test were selected, and the results were arranged in descending order from left to right according to the correlation strength, the specific results are detailed in Table 5.

Table 5 Correlation analysis of variables and indicators (N = 713)

Variables	Driving	Sig	Variables	Driving	Sig
Management	0.731**	0.000	Public Opinion	0.646**	0.000
Operating	0.728**	0.000	Safeguard Policy	0.641**	0.000
Service Items	0.699**	0.000	Infrastructure	0.632**	0.000
Resource	0.697**	0.000	Leaders attach	0.618**	0.000
Staffing	0.696**	0.000	Source of funds	0.616**	0.000
Platform Function	0.684**	0.000	Responsibility	0.614**	0.000
Service Effect	0.680**	0.000	Economic Cost	0.611**	0.000
Enforcement	0.675**	0.000	Economic Benefit	0.592**	0.000
Convenience	0.652**	0.000	Effectiveness	0.584**	0.000
Individual	0.652**	0.000	Group Constraint	0.529**	0.000
Government	0.651**	0.000	Associated Risk	0.524**	0.000
Function	0.649**	0.000			

The results of Table 5 show that there are correlations between the 23 indicators and the driving factors. Among them, except the indicators such as economic benefits, perceived effectiveness, group constraints and related risks, which belong to moderate correlation ($0.6 > p \geq 0.4$), the other indicators belong to strong correlation ($0.8 > p \geq 0.6$). From the above output results, we can see that the impact of each factor on the sustainable development of library visitor space has reached a significant level. The results of data analysis are consistent with the results of grounded research.

Summary and prospects

This paper adopts the method of combining relevant literature reading with questionnaire survey, uses grounded theory, collates and analyzes the research data through three-level coding, identifies the driving factors of sustainable development of library visitor space, and constructs the "consciousness-atmosphere-cost-field" driving factor model of sustainable development of space. Through the research, the driving factors of spatial sustainable development are divided into four categories, namely field-driven, atmosphere-driven, cost-driven and consciousness -driven. Each driving category includes the corresponding driving factors, a total of 23 driving factors are identified. Because of the limited space, the following mainly takes the field drive as the demonstration, focusing on the management system, operation mechanism, service items, staffing, resource allocation, infrastructure and other driving measures, to provide suggestions for the sustainable development of library visitor space.

In terms of management system and operation mechanism, library visitor space should choose a suitable development plan according to the actual situation of each library, formulate short-term, medium-term and long-term development plan, improve the goal and assessment mechanism, and optimize the management mode and operation mechanism. The library can also establish good cooperative relations with the community, off-campus enterprises and major research institutes, introduce professional managers or technicians from other institutions, improve the tutor team of the creative space, form a cooperative team of librarians, and establish a team of creative volunteers to assist in the completion of the work of the space. According to the institutional environment, social resources, infrastructure, funding sources and functional orientation, library creative space should choose service forms and contents, and one or more creative fields can be selected to carry out services, such as computer hardware and software technology, network information engineering, entertainment fashion, culture and art and media creativity[12]. In the choice of service items, we should also consider the relationship between library business and customer creation activities, combine their business preferences or characteristic services, and strive to design more projects in line with the characteristics of space development, so as to fundamentally improve the implementation of projects and enhance the service efficiency of library customer creation space. For example, Tongling Library's cultural and creative space joint office, social networking, learning sharing, resource docking, online and offline platforms, to cooperate with universities in a low-cost innovative mode, attract more high-quality creative teams into the space, and strengthen the cultivation and

development of cultural and technological integration projects[13]. In terms of personnel and resource allocation, library visitor space should rationally locate and allocate all kinds of resources according to its own tools, facilities and space planning and system, attract innovative and creative talents from communities, schools, enterprises and institutions to enter the space, and ensure the quantity and quality of librarians and volunteers in the normal operation of the space. Especially in the process of "double first-class" construction, the university library should speed up and perfect the cooperation with the trade and enterprises, construct the social participation mechanism, gather foreign funds and hardware and software facilities through various channels, obtain relevant and open advanced technology, attract and create guest talent [14]. Correct use of various tools, reasonable selection of activity themes, to ensure the use of facilities in the space zero error, zero error, to promote the smooth development of various service projects and activities.

In this link of the infrastructure, the maker space should act according to its ability, should choose some suitable instruments according to its own actual situation, do not need to be in place in one step, but to make the best use of things. The author believes that after the introduction of advanced digital production tools, then choose some low-cost but extremely effective hardware equipment; when the funds are abundant, we can introduce some matching equipment with perfect performance and expensive price. At the same time, in order to promote the sustainable development of space, noise and other influencing factors should be considered comprehensively in the planning and design of tourist space, and a series of negative effects caused by noise can be reduced or eliminated by dividing tourist space separately or installing sound insulation boards, so as to ensure that the interference of space to the quiet ecological environment of traditional libraries is minimized. In terms of funding sources and economic benefits, apart from the government financial allocation and the annual application for a certain amount of funding for the Creator Space Project, the Library Creator Space should continue to expand its sources of funding, such as seeking donations, grants or corporate sponsorship in the early stage of project construction, cooperating with open source hardware manufacturers and sponsors to form a partnership system, and after accumulating a certain number of users, it can adopt a membership system for the space and collect certain membership fees; It can also cooperate with the creative space in society, build a collaborative innovative service model, exchange needs, complementary shortcomings, and explore the advantages and characteristics of the library's creative space.

In a word, in order to achieve high-quality development of library creative space in China, we must aim at the driving factors in the model, make precise measures, give full play to the driving force of space equipment, resources, technology, information and system, set short-term, medium-term and long-term goals in combination with the progress of space development, adopt a scientific and reasonable way to adjust, improve and optimize the existing personnel and resource allocation, open sources and reduce expenditure, from shallow to deep, step by step. Promote the high-quality, efficient, orderly, stable and sustainable development of library creative space!

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Biographies:

Wang ning (1968-), female, from nanjing, jiangsu province. Double degree, research librarian. In July 1990, I graduated from anhui university, majoring in library science. After graduation, I was assigned to work in the library of anhui university of administration. I love study, diligent study, this paper studies modern technology in the new use and new development in the area of books, information, once successively in national and provincial magazines published 46 papers, host, 1 national social science fund in development projects, the management, complete province class 3 items, participation, complete national and provincial level topic 3 items, published three monographs.

AUTHORS' BACKGROUN

Your Name	Title*	Research Field	Personal website
Ning Wang	Identification and Model Construction of the Drivers of Sustainable Development of Library in Maker Space — — Empirical Analysis Based on The Grounded Theory	Information management	

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